

Coefficients of an ANN constitutive flow law of a Ti6–Al–4V material for dynamic applications

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Abstract

This paper gathers the results concerning the identification of the coefficients of the flow law of a Ti6–Al–4V for a flow law defined by a neural network as described and defined by Pantalé et al. [1]. This ANN allows the calculation of the flow stress σ as a function of the plastic strain ε^p , the plastic strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}^p$ and the temperature T respectively. The methodology for defining the ANN flow law is not described in this paper, only the identification of the coefficients for a Ti6–Al–4V is part of this paper.

Keywords: Artificial Neural Network, Ti6–Al–4V, Constitutive flow law, Material parameters

1. Introduction

In this paper, we are using the ANN constitutive flow law described by Pantalé et al. [1]. The architecture of this ANN is reported in Figure 1. This is a multi-layer ANN with 2 hidden layers, 3 inputs (the plastic strain ε^p , the plastic strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}^p$ and the temperature T respectively) and 1 output (the flow stress σ).

We present hereafter the coefficients of the ANN constitutive flow law w_1 , w_2 , w , $\vec{b}_1$, $\vec{b}_2$ and b related to the paper [1] for a Ti6–Al–4V material. This flow law is able to replace the Johnson-Cook flow law usually defined by the following equation:

$$\sigma^y = \left(A + B\varepsilon^{p^n} \right) \left[1 + C \ln \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon}^p}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right) \right] \left[1 - \left(\frac{T - T_0}{T_m - T_0} \right)^m \right] \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\varepsilon}_0$ is the reference strain rate, T_0 and T_m are the reference temperature and the melting temperature of the material respectively and A , B , C , n and m are the five constitutive flow law parameters reported here after for a Ti6–Al–4V as proposed by [2].

A (MPa)	B (MPa)	C	n	m	T_0 °C	T_m °C	$\dot{\varepsilon}_0$ (s ⁻¹)
997.9	653.1	0.0198	0.45	0.7	293	1873	1.0

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Figure 1: Multi-layer Artificial Neural Network architecture

The training of the neural network was performed using a data set generated according to equation (1), and including 3 430 data points defined by:

- 70 equidistant values for $\varepsilon^p \in [0.0, 3.0]$,
- 7 plastic strain rates $\dot{\varepsilon}^p \in [1, 10, 50, 500, 5\,000, 50\,000, 500\,000]$,
- 7 temperatures $T \in [293, 400, 500, 700, 900, 1\,200, 1\,500]$.

The parameters for scaling the values in the neural network are the same for all models and are given by:

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.00000 & 0.00000 & 293.00000 & 171.43941 \\ 3.00000 & 13.12236 & 1500.00000 & 2606.12051 \end{bmatrix}$$

where the values are related to ε^p , $\dot{\varepsilon}^p$, T and σ respectively.

2. Results of the identification

The application of the identification method described by Pantalé *et al.* [1] on these data then leads to the identification of several data sets for neural networks according to their architecture. In the present publication, we have used a neural network with 2 hidden layers and a sigmoid activation function on the neurons of the two hidden layers as described in [1]. The number of neurons in the second hidden layer is fixed at 7, while the number of neurons in the first layer varies between 9 and 17 in increments of 2 in the results presented in the next section. There is 3 entries for the neural network (entry layer) in the order plastic strain ε^p , the plastic strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}^p$ and the temperature T .

2.1. Coefficients of the ANN 3-9-7-1-sig

The results of the parameter identification for a network containing 9 neurons in the first hidden layer and 7 neurons in the second hidden layer are given below.

$$\mathbf{w}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.87229 & -0.47675 & -1.50771 \\ -0.95762 & -0.25619 & 1.65222 \\ -10.61660 & 0.22003 & -0.11539 \\ 3.67883 & 0.37146 & -1.51069 \\ -63.39468 & 0.15466 & -0.95431 \\ 0.54807 & 0.25959 & -5.44355 \\ -1.33883 & 0.36089 & -1.66735 \\ -0.68125 & 1.02121 & 0.34242 \\ 0.08740 & 0.18764 & -41.32542 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{w}_2^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1.66285 & -0.59645 & -3.17333 & 0.20706 & 1.18760 & 2.01250 & -0.82147 \\ -0.26237 & -2.50330 & -1.45941 & -1.59833 & 4.05169 & -1.21146 & 1.05610 \\ -0.12958 & 0.67119 & -5.85989 & -2.55061 & 4.85245 & 4.31876 & 3.24070 \\ -2.12890 & 0.68296 & 0.71183 & 0.81706 & -0.09405 & 0.34919 & -1.41223 \\ 2.33631 & -0.08089 & 14.65789 & 0.12531 & 23.66363 & 2.55872 & 2.15338 \\ 0.11567 & 1.77629 & -1.80448 & 0.77825 & -1.58254 & 1.90442 & 1.23152 \\ 1.49265 & 0.41821 & -3.53803 & -0.48705 & -0.23671 & 0.75887 & -0.37441 \\ 0.95990 & 0.69041 & 0.43870 & 0.28393 & -1.40101 & -0.64569 & -0.38964 \\ 5.89937 & -0.13015 & 2.99264 & 1.78534 & -3.90189 & 1.17494 & -3.78854 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{w} = [0.34701 \quad 1.42079 \quad -0.96564 \quad 0.62467 \quad -0.56322 \quad 0.40960 \quad -0.42810]$$

$$\vec{b}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 2.57141 \\ 0.22673 \\ -1.16985 \\ -0.11246 \\ -0.82210 \\ -2.13264 \\ 0.78794 \\ 1.20434 \\ -3.48681 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{b}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.36566 \\ -1.14445 \\ -0.79065 \\ -0.50670 \\ 1.30136 \\ 0.04521 \\ -0.29995 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$b = 0.04213$$

2.2. Coefficients of the ANN 3-11-7-1-sig

The results of the parameter identification for a network containing 11 neurons in the first hidden layer and 7 neurons in the second hidden layer are given below.

$$\mathbf{w}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 5.48063 & -0.00162 & -1.01749 \\ -8.11656 & 0.04490 & -0.34194 \\ -36.76621 & 0.08780 & -1.05180 \\ 0.18652 & -1.17200 & -0.80563 \\ -0.11288 & -0.06079 & 44.19233 \\ -0.01874 & -1.29382 & 0.54051 \\ 1.70204 & 0.03902 & 2.11885 \\ -1.33601 & 0.00045 & 2.12470 \\ -1.01124 & 0.06240 & 3.59696 \\ -0.31606 & 0.59575 & -2.14882 \\ -1.32552 & -0.10665 & -5.84340 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{w}_2^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1.27284 & -0.37584 & -1.54607 & 1.28581 & 1.82391 & 0.77950 & -1.07659 \\ 1.56778 & 6.65338 & -0.21224 & -0.19965 & 1.30757 & -0.92618 & 0.10794 \\ -0.03199 & -15.53275 & -0.33659 & -0.28577 & 0.28241 & -0.21972 & 0.82597 \\ -0.77040 & 0.46888 & 0.63377 & -1.35185 & 0.85714 & -0.20245 & -0.28732 \\ -1.02857 & 0.55164 & 1.41397 & -1.23025 & 0.14593 & -0.82914 & 1.28189 \\ -1.19739 & 0.62185 & 0.68196 & -1.42013 & -0.04528 & -2.12501 & 0.71378 \\ 0.90869 & -1.66608 & 0.97232 & -1.12554 & -1.45043 & -1.05947 & 0.15070 \\ -1.92885 & -1.30645 & 0.64370 & -2.07013 & -1.15299 & -2.69921 & 1.33294 \\ -1.51784 & 1.74196 & 1.66202 & -2.27333 & -0.13736 & -1.04460 & 0.24749 \\ 0.00791 & 2.00578 & -1.31173 & 1.45129 & 0.82853 & 0.58595 & -1.18210 \\ -0.58402 & 0.74926 & -0.59914 & 1.21108 & 1.34182 & -1.32262 & 0.59964 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{w} = [0.95231 \quad 0.90037 \quad -0.64923 \quad 1.26332 \quad 0.74010 \quad 0.72079 \quad -0.64582]$$

$$\vec{b}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.19796 \\ 1.88844 \\ 0.27413 \\ 1.63296 \\ 2.97499 \\ -1.22086 \\ -3.39824 \\ -0.12243 \\ 1.63729 \\ 0.58229 \\ 1.09879 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{b}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.23108 \\ 2.21919 \\ -0.00773 \\ -0.29612 \\ 0.38348 \\ -0.61839 \\ -0.13336 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$b = -0.29994$$

2.3. Coefficients of the ANN 3-13-7-1-sig

The results of the parameter identification for a network containing 13 neurons in the first hidden layer and 7 neurons in the second hidden layer are given below.

$$w_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.27936 & -0.65379 & 2.79214 \\ -1.68367 & -0.30331 & -1.78935 \\ 0.14392 & -0.23959 & -9.80223 \\ -0.22080 & -0.43042 & 2.73769 \\ 14.75872 & -0.32362 & 2.14731 \\ 2.31654 & 0.03593 & -1.31716 \\ -2.34998 & -0.07148 & -2.01882 \\ -0.01423 & -0.00970 & -39.80015 \\ -0.11760 & -1.62231 & 0.34046 \\ -80.44365 & 0.12862 & -0.96886 \\ 1.75698 & 0.28883 & -3.48984 \\ 0.74996 & 0.65697 & -2.22866 \\ -5.26583 & -0.13555 & 1.67257 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$w_2^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0.65476 & 1.19738 & 2.35194 & -1.36091 & -0.37392 & -0.57320 & -1.66689 \\ -1.24736 & 0.30247 & 0.61982 & -0.14358 & 0.63368 & 1.77397 & 0.18717 \\ -0.09282 & -0.66868 & -2.27802 & 0.15736 & -0.22819 & 0.39699 & -0.48730 \\ 0.11199 & 0.19679 & 0.75656 & -1.99130 & -0.57302 & -0.79521 & -2.02158 \\ -2.11155 & -0.95111 & -0.26157 & 0.37965 & 1.56624 & 0.99147 & 0.06640 \\ -0.70807 & -1.08745 & -0.30507 & 0.63147 & 1.39773 & 0.29510 & 0.08030 \\ -0.45656 & -0.48562 & -0.48053 & 0.13081 & 0.15067 & 1.28901 & -0.58534 \\ 0.73208 & -0.48859 & -2.48763 & -2.34592 & -0.05286 & 1.05723 & 0.76659 \\ 0.38625 & 1.29755 & 1.14063 & -1.32817 & 0.29114 & 0.39041 & -2.29790 \\ -7.55752 & -1.04362 & 1.92458 & -4.12448 & -10.12198 & 10.68679 & -1.15369 \\ -0.22300 & -1.32314 & -1.11161 & 1.05198 & 1.02679 & -0.05935 & -0.00966 \\ -0.84401 & -1.05408 & 0.01480 & 0.17490 & 0.91986 & 0.53774 & 0.81916 \\ 0.23811 & 0.56246 & 2.39061 & -3.09159 & -0.43607 & 0.44335 & -3.08219 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$w = \begin{bmatrix} -1.03509 & -0.33756 & -0.94049 & 0.58569 & 0.74691 & 0.83666 & 0.40951 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{b}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1.56538 \\ 3.99146 \\ -1.42714 \\ -0.54917 \\ 1.22075 \\ -0.76749 \\ 1.85681 \\ -1.46041 \\ -0.97879 \\ -2.39805 \\ -1.44943 \\ -1.02275 \\ -1.00777 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{b}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.01686 \\ -0.04627 \\ 0.87205 \\ -0.71862 \\ -0.24971 \\ -0.24672 \\ -1.12345 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$b = -0.01526$$

2.4. Coefficients of the ANN 3-15-7-1-sig

The results of the parameter identification for a network containing 15 neurons in the first hidden layer and 7 neurons in the second hidden layer are given below.

$$\mathbf{w}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.24571 & 0.78788 & -4.00685 \\ 0.48208 & 0.25153 & -3.02677 \\ -1.50328 & -0.49685 & -1.39077 \\ -0.52207 & -0.74587 & -1.26557 \\ 0.58307 & -0.72761 & -1.29275 \\ 0.07133 & -0.49261 & 2.87159 \\ -0.95785 & -0.14484 & 2.57696 \\ 0.70148 & 0.72191 & 18.12262 \\ -3.08598 & 0.04621 & 0.26670 \\ -53.63026 & -0.11171 & -1.48486 \\ -10.69876 & 0.09889 & 0.50993 \\ -0.92389 & -0.52912 & 2.70815 \\ 0.24805 & 1.65717 & -0.75772 \\ 0.17055 & 0.50492 & -2.74640 \\ 0.63514 & 0.53923 & 40.66933 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{w}_2^T = \begin{bmatrix} -0.86805 & 0.53016 & -1.30237 & 1.40443 & -2.72489 & -1.07973 & 0.73422 \\ -1.23470 & 0.47873 & -1.80757 & 1.35385 & -2.89608 & -2.41443 & 2.86339 \\ 1.49638 & 0.22329 & 0.27898 & 0.19880 & -1.82086 & -1.34763 & 1.42514 \\ 1.20500 & -0.51106 & -0.95472 & 0.43763 & -2.88503 & -1.31466 & 1.95261 \\ -0.88647 & 0.26851 & -0.50895 & -0.13995 & -1.97530 & -0.19937 & 3.28423 \\ -2.76718 & -1.05323 & 0.58157 & -1.04656 & 1.84956 & 1.20466 & -1.54718 \\ -0.73423 & -0.62850 & 0.72679 & -1.93286 & -0.13601 & 0.18911 & 0.89903 \\ -0.34303 & -0.85362 & -0.05891 & -1.54512 & -0.67357 & -0.47843 & -1.05128 \\ 2.72967 & -1.83914 & 0.12159 & -0.58250 & -0.28631 & -1.69019 & 1.94126 \\ -0.18452 & -0.43488 & 0.08930 & 0.01628 & -2.48392 & 0.16673 & -15.57520 \\ 6.24451 & -3.25461 & -0.42372 & -2.17540 & 0.36483 & -3.74025 & 8.95765 \\ -1.21728 & -0.68882 & -0.29480 & -1.56904 & -0.20873 & -1.15214 & 1.22660 \\ -0.47410 & 0.72538 & -0.48032 & 0.03553 & -0.36700 & -2.04596 & -0.30574 \\ -1.32622 & 0.59500 & -1.90348 & 1.40203 & -3.12916 & -1.97803 & 1.79461 \\ -0.03775 & 0.43400 & -0.28314 & -1.91390 & -0.55851 & -0.43227 & 0.57427 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{w} = [-0.38959 \quad 0.94745 \quad -0.75800 \quad 1.93686 \quad -1.02702 \quad -0.70094 \quad 0.46453]$$

$$\vec{b}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.01002 \\ -0.76626 \\ 0.73783 \\ 0.96764 \\ 0.18457 \\ -1.93871 \\ 0.28742 \\ 1.80256 \\ -0.52610 \\ -0.09136 \\ -2.29484 \\ 0.97820 \\ 0.87482 \\ -0.48883 \\ 0.58303 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{b}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.99604 \\ -0.30989 \\ -0.34126 \\ -0.17164 \\ -0.82569 \\ -0.92044 \\ 1.49505 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$b = -0.18036$$

2.5. Coefficients of the ANN 3-17-7-1-sig

The results of the parameter identification for a network containing 17 neurons in the first hidden layer and 7 neurons in the second hidden layer are given below.

$$\mathbf{w}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.80547 & -0.82484 & 4.90679 \\ -0.56658 & -0.62979 & 2.01304 \\ -0.55095 & 0.48985 & -3.00138 \\ -1.85721 & -0.66557 & 1.30634 \\ 0.45814 & -1.43388 & 0.00127 \\ -1.41504 & 0.65986 & 4.10080 \\ 0.68556 & 0.81797 & -2.83883 \\ -5.63527 & 0.10224 & -2.07840 \\ -0.52393 & -0.35790 & -26.49131 \\ -1.29336 & 0.51827 & -1.66159 \\ 1.76181 & -0.36999 & -3.16714 \\ -0.43960 & -0.34121 & 16.90590 \\ -33.83498 & -0.03539 & -0.82982 \\ 3.79918 & -0.37201 & 0.81669 \\ -2.03341 & -0.75614 & -1.42118 \\ 2.46618 & -0.29659 & -1.47919 \\ 0.69916 & 0.73239 & -3.01668 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{w}_2^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0.80063 & -0.57510 & -0.52163 & -1.64368 & -1.60575 & 2.77130 & 0.30916 \\ 0.77963 & -0.55755 & 0.61738 & -1.61003 & -0.98736 & 1.30355 & 0.70975 \\ -0.33841 & -0.23182 & -2.80825 & 0.66304 & 0.20820 & 1.02752 & -0.90320 \\ 0.92369 & -0.53429 & -1.14204 & -2.83687 & -0.47462 & 2.59937 & 0.90091 \\ -0.02056 & 1.39182 & -1.22021 & -1.25942 & -0.71847 & -0.25960 & -0.53788 \\ 0.52379 & -0.08571 & 0.61992 & -2.07852 & -2.55392 & 0.58005 & -0.74540 \\ -0.54894 & 0.98498 & -0.30027 & 0.42777 & -0.05071 & 2.68940 & -2.24672 \\ 1.51259 & -4.92825 & -2.53239 & -4.84727 & -0.59164 & 4.76440 & 2.12180 \\ 0.30918 & -0.35404 & 2.41577 & -0.42409 & 2.82638 & 0.39388 & -0.37510 \\ -1.25125 & 0.38656 & -2.74431 & 0.75430 & 0.28123 & 0.81674 & -1.05074 \\ -0.17617 & 1.80148 & -0.50988 & 0.57102 & 0.24392 & 1.97156 & -0.17517 \\ 1.00467 & -0.11685 & -0.60060 & -0.26010 & -2.22839 & 1.18040 & 0.41309 \\ 0.64265 & -0.65898 & -0.67298 & -26.10401 & -0.24569 & -20.18595 & -0.20897 \\ 0.07754 & -0.99504 & 1.04895 & -0.35164 & -0.78671 & -1.35084 & 0.37027 \\ 0.37721 & 0.88930 & -3.46352 & -0.69313 & -0.46486 & 2.39146 & 0.09822 \\ -1.00379 & 0.85844 & -0.50283 & 0.55968 & 0.42410 & -1.09965 & -1.26477 \\ -0.84216 & 1.31505 & -0.94523 & 0.88245 & -0.21800 & 1.85100 & -2.03780 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{w} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.60713 & 0.19256 & -1.42113 & 0.45944 & 1.34197 & 0.74130 & -0.49565 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{b}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.83172 \\ -0.56079 \\ -0.90392 \\ 0.26668 \\ 1.90542 \\ -0.78231 \\ -0.97359 \\ -0.85215 \\ 0.51096 \\ 1.70385 \\ 0.49530 \\ 1.06219 \\ -0.15789 \\ -0.59555 \\ 0.95336 \\ 1.30516 \\ -0.94207 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{b}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.26822 \\ -0.08946 \\ -0.42215 \\ -0.52579 \\ -0.76522 \\ 1.70954 \\ -0.20075 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$b = -0.00298$$

3. Conclusion

This paper lists the coefficients of a neural network describing the flow law of a Ti6–Al–4V in a Johnson–Cook type flow law formalism. Several network architectures are proposed for which the number of neurons in the first hidden layer varies between 9 and 17. The set of these coefficients allows then to program this neural network as a product of matrices in order to allow the calculation of the flow stress σ as a function of the plastic strain ε^p , the plastic strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}^p$ and the temperature T respectively.

References

- [1] Olivier Pantalé, Pierre Tize Mha, Amèvi Tongne. *Efficient implementation of non-linear flow law using neural network into the Abaqus Explicit FEM code*. Finite Elements in Analysis and Design 198, 103647, 2022.
- [2] Songwon Seo, Oakkey Min, Hyunmo Yang. *Constitutive equation for Ti-6Al-4V at high temperatures measured using the SHPB technique*. International Journal of Impact Engineering, vol 31, (6), 735–754, 2005.